

HPC-JEEP: Disseminating energy usage on the ARCHER2 and COSMA HPC services

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1. Introduction

National supercomputing and HPC services such as [ARCHER2](#) and [DiRAC](#) represent large investments in DRI by UKRI to serve UK research and use large amounts of electricity (for example, ARCHER2 can draw up to ~4 MW at peak load). Traditionally, resources on such services have been granted in units of compute time (core-hours, node-hours, etc.) with users not informed, nor paying much attention to their energy use; and services not generally reporting breakdowns of energy use other than for total electricity charges. Without an understanding of how research areas, projects and users use energy and how efficiently they use resources it is difficult to plan future procurements or service strategies towards a net zero goal. The HPC-JEEP project is looking at what level of energy information can be extracted from current and historical per-job data from ARCHER2 and DiRAC services; and how this data can be analysed and synthesised to provide the information required for funders (who procure and set service strategy and objectives) and researchers (who make decisions about how best to use the resources they are granted) to allow them to make informed decisions about how to manage HPC resources to extract the maximum research benefit in the most emissions efficient way. The challenges the project is trying to address are:

1. What evidence can we provide from current HPC energy usage data to support users and funders towards net zero?
2. What could be the potential impacts of moving to job charging based on energy/emissions use to support net zero goals based on current evidence?
3. What are the best energy/emissions metrics that could be provided to HPC users and funders to help them support net zero goals?

In this paper we address primarily Challenge 3: *What are the best energy/emissions metrics that could be provided to HPC users and funders to help them support net zero goals?* In particular, we look at the quarterly reporting to users and project PIs that has been done for the past 3 quarters, and the information that is provided. We also look at tools available for users to get a report on the energy consumption of their Slurm jobs and also investigate energy usage within different stages of their simulations. Finally, we look at conversion of energy usage to CO₂ produced, using national and regional data, and consider the effects that certified 100% renewable energy contracts have on this.

The paper is laid out in the following way: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the energy consumption data captured. Section 3 describes the methodologies used to extract and analyse the energy use data; Section 4 discusses the dissemination approaches used and how users can obtain their own data. Section 5 presents an analysis of CO₂ produced. Section 6 provides some conclusions from the work so far and thoughts on implications of the rest of the project. The whole paper is supported by a dataset containing the raw data that was used for the analysis and the scripts and tooling that performed the analysis itself.

2. Energy consumption data captured

ARCHER2

ARCHER2 is a UK national supercomputing service funded by UKRI (via EPSRC and NERC) with the HPC platform provided by HPE and the hosting and support provided by EPCC at The University of Edinburgh. The ARCHER2 system is a liquid-cooled HPE Cray EX with 5,860 compute nodes giving a total of 750,080 compute cores.

The energy consumption captured here is in-system only, and thus does not include inefficiencies due to the plant backing the hardware; e.g. PDU (ARCHER2 compute nodes are not on UPS, they are on raw electricity feeds) and external cooling infrastructure.

ARCHER2 energy is provided by a certified 100% renewable energy contract.

Energy consumption data is captured by a SLURM plugin, which measures the energy used by each compute node during the operation of a job. It can therefore be queried using standard SLURM commands by users.

COSMA

COSMA is a UK national supercomputing service funded by UKRI (via STFC through DiRAC), with the HPC platform currently provided by Dell and the hosting and support provided by the Institute of Computational Cosmology at Durham University. Several generations of COSMA are currently in operation, and here we concentrate on the two newest installations, COSMA7 and COSMA8. COSMA7 has 452 compute nodes (12k cores) and COSMA8 has 360 compute nodes (46k cores).

The energy consumption captured here is in-system only. However, we also capture the incoming energy of the power supply, and are able to relate that to an operational power usage effectiveness (PUE). Historically, energy is provided on a 100% renewable energy contract, however this has changed within the past 12 months, to a standard contract.

Energy consumption is captured at the start and end of each job on each compute node, allowing the total energy consumed by that job to be calculated. This is stored externally to SLURM, and thus users need to use different tools to capture this information.

Energy consumption of the COSMA storage is also captured, and the energy consumption of the network fabric estimated.

3. Methodology

ARCHER2

On ARCHER2, the node energy data is taken from the HPE Cray Power Management counters provided by the HPE Cray Baseboard Management Controller (BMC). The Slurm “pm_counters” energy plugin¹ combines the data from all compute nodes involved in each job to produce an overall node energy use for the job which is stored in the Slurm accounting database in the “ConsumedEnergyRaw” and “ConsumedEnergy” fields. The node energy use covers all components in the compute node, including processors, memory, interconnect cards and other parts.

The energy usage by system components external to compute nodes is not currently included or accounted for in the energy use data. Items not accounted for include the interconnect switches, file systems, login nodes and other parts external to the compute nodes (e.g. cooling infrastructure). As described in a previous HPC-JEEP report², the compute nodes account for 83% of the power draw on ARCHER2 so the compute node energy use will provide a good proxy for the total amount of energy used by a job.

This information is not reported to users, however they are able to query the Slurm database themselves if they wish.

COSMA

Node energy use is taken from the Dell hardware using ipmitool. Cumulative energy of each node is captured at the start and end of each job, and thus, the total energy per job can be measured. We also measure the energy consumed by switches and storage and thus a statistical approach can be used to divide the energy consumed by these among the jobs running on the system.

This information is reported to users on a quarterly basis by email, providing information about their total energy usage, and approximations for the amount of CO2 produced.

¹ https://github.com/SchedMD/slurm/tree/master/src/plugins/acct_gather_energy/pm_counters

² HPC-JEEP: Energy Usage on ARCHER2 and the DiRAC COSMA HPC services:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128628>

4. Dissemination approaches

We here concentrate on the dissemination approach taken for COSMA, for ARCHER2, information is not currently routinely passed to individual users - though they are free to access it via Slurm tools.

On COSMA, a quarterly email is sent to individual users who have produced more than 10kg CO₂ (we describe how we convert energy to CO₂ emissions below). A quarterly email is also sent to project Principal Investigators, detailing the energy consumption of their project, an estimate for the associated CO₂ produced, and a breakdown of user consumption for the project. The current aim of these emails is to raise awareness of the energy use and associated emissions by users and projects and to set the values that we send them in a useful context so that they have some sense of the scale of their use/emissions. Per project summaries are also shared with the service funders via the local DiRAC COSMA Service Management Board to make funders aware of the impact of use of the service on energy consumption and emissions, and with the Oversight Committee 6-monthly reports.

An example of these emails (anonymised) are shown below.

PI email

Dear XXX (as dpNNN PI),

Your DiRAC project dpNNN has used a total of approximately 12.3 MW·h over the past 3 months on COSMA. This figure represents compute nodes only, and does not include storage or the networking fabric.

During this period, the average carbon intensity of electricity in the North East of England was 27.2 g CO₂ / kW·h and therefore, your project dpNNN has generated approximately 336 kg CO₂.

This is broken down as:

cosma8 : 12341.4 kW·h 25203.3 nodehr 489.673 avW/node

Per-user information is given below, sorted by highest total power consumption.

At some point, UKRI may change from allocating CPU hours to kW·h, so we hope this information will be useful.

Best wishes,
cosma-support

Username	Total	System	kW·h	nodehr	avW/node	(repeated per system)
dc-AAAA2	6652.02	cosma8	6652.02	11369.1	585.098	
dc-BBBB1	3577.75	cosma8	3577.75	8547.91	418.552	
dc-CCCC1	2111.63	cosma8	2111.63	5286.34	399.45	

If there are specific users with lower than average W/node, then it may be worth contacting them to check they are using the node efficiently (e.g. not running a single-core Python job on a node with 128 cores!)

User email

Dear XXX,

Over the past quarter (3 months), your jobs have used approximately 4.39 MW·h on COSMA (excluding COSMA5 and COSMA6).

This figure represents compute nodes only, and does not include storage, the networking fabric, or the cooling. When these are included, the value is (even more approximately) 5.68 MW·h.

During this period, the average carbon intensity of electricity in the North East of England was 27.2 g CO₂ / kW·h and therefore your usage has generated approximately 154 kg CO₂.

Partition cosma8: 4.39 MW·h (5586 node hours) averaging 786 W/node (nodes only, excluding storage etc)

At some point, DiRAC may change from an allocation of CPU core hours to an allocation of kW·h, so we hope this information will be useful in estimating what quota you will require when the time comes. It may also be worth looking at optimising codes for efficiency.

We had a request to add some context, though you can probably work out for yourself what this means! However your usage would enable you to drive approximately 22701 miles in a 2018 Nissan Leaf, or would provide the grid electrical power for the house of the COSMA technical manager for approximately 5 years, or produce the same CO₂ as approximately 0.2 people taking a trans-atlantic flight (perhaps time to stop flying!). Please ask if you'd like more information about these calculations!

We note that as the UK has a national grid, using the CO₂ intensity measurements for one region might not be a valid approach. Therefore, if we take Great Britain as a whole, the average carbon intensity over this period was 166 g CO₂ / kWh and therefore by this metric your usage has generated approximately 944 kg CO₂.

Best wishes,
cosma-support

Assumptions

There are some assumptions made in the generation of these emails. Carbon intensity is taken from the carbonintensity.org.uk dashboard. This information is captured every 30 minutes, and an average value then taken over the quarter in question. This information is available both for the North East region and the UK as a whole, and both estimates are used in the email to users.

The data centre PUE is estimated using the energy from the main incomer (total energy supplied) divided by the energy provided at the power distribution units (PDU) that directly power the server racks. Therefore, the UPS and Coolers/Chillers are included in the main incomer, but not in the PDU values. This information is averaged over the quarter in question.

The InfiniBand switches are assumed to take 230W, a value measured from the web interface of the switches themselves.

The COSMA7 storage is assumed to average 22kW, while the COSMA8 storage averages 15kW. This is based on information provided by the in-rack PDUs.

The data for comparisons (e.g. Nissan Leaf miles, Atlantic flights) are taken from publicly available information³

User access

Users are also able to access the information of their energy consumed on a per-job basis. There are currently no bespoke tools for this, though we plan to make some available. Instead, users can grep for their username or Slurm job number from a summary file at a known location, or if they need immediate access to data for a job that has just completed, access unprocessed files (which are summarised nightly) based on their job number.

³ <https://www.autoexpress.co.uk/nissan/leaf/100747/new-nissan-leaf-2018-review>
<https://calculator.carbonfootprint.com/calculator.aspx?tab=3>

5. Analysis of CO₂ produced

Capturing energy usage is relatively easy, since this is a quantity that is measurable within the data centre. However, converting this to a CO₂ measurement is more difficult. We currently provide two measurements. The first is based on regional carbon intensity data provided by a public web portal, which measures the mass of CO₂ produced per kWh used. For the North East of England, this value is low compared with most of the rest of the country primarily due to large offshore wind farms. The second measurement is based on the national carbon intensity data. Both of these values are captured at 30 minute intervals (the granularity of the web portal), and then averaged to get an average measurement over the period in question. It should be noted that as the UK has a national grid, not an isolated regional grid, using the national carbon intensity measurements is probably a more valid approach, though this significantly increases the estimate of the amount of CO₂ produced by each job.

It may be more accurate to use the carbon intensity measurements at the point in time at which each job is running, and thus calculate the CO₂ produced that way. We may investigate this in future quarters. However, it should be noted that as users have little control when their jobs actually run (during busy periods, a submitted job may not be scheduled for 3 days or more), taking the average CO₂ measurement is probably a valid thing to do. There is the potential to investigate emissions-aware scheduling approaches in the future - at this point, the temporal resolution of emissions tied to particular jobs will matter as users will then have some degree of control and choice about under what types of emissions intensity regimes their jobs run. However, we note that this part of the emissions associated with HPC systems is likely to decrease in the future as more and more energy generation moves to zero carbon sources. As we discuss below, embodied emissions - which already play a large role in the overall emissions from an HPC system - will become a larger and larger component as the electricity grid decarbonises.

Previously, Durham University has operated on a zero carbon electricity tariff. However, how such a tariff actually impacts emissions is not as straightforward as it might first appear. Each period (say, a year) the energy supplier has a limited amount of zero carbon energy that they can sell which, in a simplified sense, corresponds to the predicted amount of zero carbon energy production that is available over the period. Any energy used by an HPC system under a zero carbon tariff pushes other users to be using energy capacity that generates emissions. Investment in zero carbon energy tariffs does, however, have a positive impact on emissions for the future as it includes premiums that help fund the expansion and improvement of zero carbon energy sources within the country (though we note that a large customer such as UKRI would see better outcomes by directly investing the additional money into carbon-free technologies). HPC services on zero carbon energy tariffs can also free up zero carbon energy capacity by improving their energy efficiency. In this work we use the national and regional carbon intensities associated with electricity from UK National Grid energy production.

We currently do not include any embodied carbon analysis in these data. Dell are able to provide the embodied carbon for a generic server of the type that we use for compute nodes.

However, this estimate will have significant error because it will not be for the exact processor type, memory or RAM that COSMA has. There are future plans for Dell to include a more bespoke embodied carbon estimation tool, at which point, this information can be included in the quarterly emails. We note that as a rough calculation using the currently available information, it would be necessary to operate COSMA7 for 18 years before the CO₂ produced due to electricity during the system lifetime is equal to the embodied CO₂, using the carbon intensity for the North East. This figure reduces to about 4 years using the national carbon intensity.

6. Conclusions

COSMA has been providing quarterly emails detailing user energy consumption, and thus approximate CO₂ produced by their jobs.

Feedback from users has been positive, and many have found it valuable to be told how much CO₂ they are producing. Whether this information has changed user behaviour (for example, not running unnecessary jobs) is unknown, but at the very least, it raises awareness that HPC is not a free resource.

Quarterly emails are probably about the right frequency; frequent enough to provide useful information, but not too frequent as to be ignored.

More easily accessible tools, well documented, to enable users to explore the CO₂ produced by their own jobs, should be considered as a future extension to this work.